

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS-PHILOLOGISTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6660552>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 15th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Philology, practice, Russian as a foreign language, methodology, development, Russian language, profession, activity.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the scientific and methodological problems of organizing the professional training of philologists. A trainee-philologist is a future specialist who conducts educational, educational work in the environment where his educational, pedagogical, scientific and cognitive activities are organized.

Reform, restructuring of many foundations is currently taking place not only in Uzbek society, but also in educational theory and practice, in their content-subject and methodological-methodological areas, including in such a field of science and practice as the methodology of teaching the Russian language as a foreign language, although the path of formation and development of teaching methods for Russian as a foreign language has always been evolutionary and thorny. Suffice it to recall that, being included in the number of "sciences at the intersection of disciplines", it relied in its research on the developments of linguistics, didactics, psychology, philosophy, etc., which often led to the denial of methodology as a science by some representatives of other areas of knowledge.

However, the rapid development of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign

language since the beginning of the 60s. The 20th century showed that it not only has its own status, subject, principles, methods and techniques of teaching, but also enriches other branches of knowledge and activity with accumulated developments, experience, including the methodology of teaching Russian as a native language.

The methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language also contributed to the didactic foundations of higher education. The dialogue principle, which grew up in the depths of a broad understanding of the phenomenon of communication, began to "infiltrate" the professional interaction of teachers and students through the efforts of Russian studies. It also influenced the formation of a special, emotional attitude to teaching, which began to be thought of as cooperation, co-creation. The wishes of Yu.M. Lotman, expressed in 1993 regarding

the peculiarities of university education: "There is no top and bottom here - teachers and students - here all colleagues, i.e. people who work together. After all, the work of a higher educational institution is in cooperation, i.e. when some want to learn, while others help them in this. It can be argued, therefore, that scientific and methodological developments in the field of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language have been innovative in recent decades.

At the same time, new horizons of research and activity are opening up before Russian studies, this is due to the change in the role and content of education in Russia and in the world. The change in educational paradigms is caused by a number of factors. Among them - a sharp increase in the volume and speed of circulation of information in society, the activity of the media, which form an almost daily picture of the world, the constantly accelerating update of social, humanitarian and scientific and technical knowledge, the introduction of new educational subjects and teaching aids into practice, rapid obsolescence professional and general cultural knowledge.

The methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language cannot fail to take into account the fact that the recent idea of continuity of education, which has become a principle, is being actively introduced into life and education. According to this principle, lifelong education is by no means adequate to the concept of lifelong learning, since continuity of education is carried out not only through and within the framework of, for example, university education, which, as was believed, provided education "for life". There is a need for a transition to continuous

education "throughout life" (even a new term has arisen - andragogy as the most adequate concept of "adult education", in contrast to "pedagogy", "teacher", i.e. "leading child").

More and more actively in the practice of higher education, and not only in the teaching of a foreign language, the idea of personality-oriented learning, more precisely, continuous personality-oriented education, is being introduced. The above trends and changes in education suggest changes both in the theory and in the practice of teaching Russian as a foreign language, indicate the need for a fundamental update in the training of specialists who will become conductors of innovation in teaching the Russian language and culture, i.e. philologists, Russian philologists.

Higher professional education is by its nature a systemic object, complex both in structure, content, functions, and in diverse interaction with the entire social environment. The study of higher education is possible only from the standpoint of a systematic approach. This approach, to one degree or another, was reflected in the works of scientists of different generations who made a great contribution to the development of didactics of higher education: S.I. Arkhangel'sky, Yu.K. Babansky, V.P. Bepalko, P.P. Blonsky, A.A. Verbitsky, E.A. Golanta, A.K. Grigorieva, K.M. Gurevich, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, T.A. Ilina, E.A. Klimova, N.V. Kuzmina, I.Ya. Lerner, N.D. Nikandrov, P.I. the object and subject of didactics of today's higher education was given by V.I. Zagvyazinsky and L.I. sphere of production, culture, education or science. The subject of didactics of higher education is the structure, content, driving forces, methods

and forms of effective interaction between teachers and students in the educational system aimed at shaping the personality of a specialist (Fundamentals of didactics of higher education, p. 7).

The fact is that the formation of a future specialist, his formation as a person at the moment is influenced not only by training and the program content of education transmitted by the teacher, but also by the intellectual and creative activity and self-education of the subject. Modern conditions for the development of society, the mobility of professions and specializations, dictated by the new forms of the country's economic structure, indicate that relying on the assimilation of a certain amount of knowledge and skills is no longer enough. A transition is needed from education "for life" to continuous education "throughout life".

Increasing requirements for the quality of labor has also led to the renewal of many professions. Among them is the profession of "philologist", which, despite the colossal scientific and scientific-pedagogical heritage left by philologists, has not been studied so far either from the point of view of how new values, new knowledge created by Russian scientists entered the educational culture. philologists, how they were defended, preserved, transformed and implemented in teaching and research activities, neither in terms of the content, structure, status of this profession in the new conditions of life.

Like any science, philology is one of the important parts of Russian scientific history, and the history of philological

education, the profession of "philologist" is one of the components of the history of Russian education. This is also the history of the intelligentsia - that social stratum, which, despite its relative small number, has always played a significant role in shaping science, directing it towards virtue, towards morality. According to D.S. Likhachev, philology brings humanity together, it is the highest form of humanitarian education, it (philology) underlies not only science, but also the entire human culture. In a word, philology is the connection of all connections, necessary for everyone who uses the language.

A trainee-philologist is a future specialist who conducts educational, educational work in the environment where his educational, pedagogical, scientific and cognitive activities are organized. Such a definition characterizes a student-trainee of the Faculty of Philology only in general terms. In fact, during practice, not only the professional, but also the personal development of the future specialist is intensified: a pedagogical image, an individual style of pedagogical interaction, forms of communicative and speech behavior, pedagogical tact, pedagogical rhetoric, projective culture of the current student-future teacher are formed; there is an introduction of the student to teaching technologies, including a group of skills, among which the ability to navigate the forms of organization of the educational process and the establishment of equal partnerships in the educational team is important.

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